

POLICY BRIEF

Boosting the Science Communication Ecosystem in Europe - full steam ahead

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1 Introduction

Science communication, or scicomm, plays a pivotal role in informing society, promoting scientific literacy, fostering dialogue and citizen participation, [increasing public trust in science](#) and ensuring democratic societies. Whilst multiple benefits have been demonstrated with evidence-based studies, **barriers to achieve its full potential at the individual, institutional and structural levels impact the effectiveness and motivation of multiple communities**, from researchers to science communication professionals, as well as public and private organisations, funders, research managers, journalists and local communities. During its lifetime, the Horizon Europe-funded [COALESCE](#) project, whose main goal is establishing the [European Competence Centre for Science Communication](#), will be providing participatory- and evidence-informed policy recommendations, aimed at promoting the role of science communication in the R&I systems and a need for sustainable support of its practice and professionalisation.

The current policy brief represents an exercise of consolidating and outlining key findings from the [Science with and for Society \(SwafS-19\)](#) sister projects ([QUEST](#), [CONCISE](#), [NEWSERA](#), [GlobalSCAPE](#),

[RETHINK](#), [PARCOS](#), [ENJOI](#) and [TRESCA](#)), funded under the H2020 programme to take stock and re-examine the role of science communication. The commitment of these sister projects and their members for sustaining a collective legacy gave origin to the COALESCE project. **The findings and recommendations hereby collected are consistent with those published by highly reputed organisations/public bodies**, at the international level, such as Science Europe¹, the OECD² and the JRC³, as well as, at the national level, the Spanish Foundation of Science and Technology (FECYT)⁴ and the German Federal Government⁵.

We also show the role science communication can play and contribute to implementing the [ERA Policy Agenda](#) (2022–2024), specially to ERA actions 14 (bringing science closer to citizens) and 17

¹ Science Europe (2022). Position Statement “Science Communication for Greater Research Impact”, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645074>

² OECD (2023). “Communicating science responsibly”, OECD Policy Briefs, No. 2, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/5c3be7ce-en>.

³ Smillie, L. and Scharfbillig, M., (2024). Trustworthy Public Communications, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, doi:10.2760/695605, JRC137725.

⁴ FECYT (2024). Conclusiones “El Futuro de la Comunicación Científica”, <https://comunicacioncientifica.fecyt.es/actualidad/conclusiones-de-el-futuro-de-la-comunicacion-cientifica>

⁵ German Bundestag (2024). “Systematically and comprehensively strengthening science communication” <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/20/106/2010606.pdf>

(focusing on paving credible career pathways into the broad field of research management), the [4 ERA Actions proposed for 2025–2027](#), the European Commission's [6 priorities for 2019–2024](#), and are aligned with the [Political Guidelines for European Commission 2024–2029](#), by the EU re-elected President Ursula von der Leyen.

Recently, expert reports from Draghi⁶, Letta⁷ and Heitor⁸ have highlighted the urgent need to enhance EU competitiveness by prioritising research and innovation (R&I), offering bold visions for outlining the trajectory and funding for the next R&I framework programme (FP10). Whilst one of Heitor's report recommendations was to "form a **Societal Challenges Council** to address key societal issues, align with EU strategic priorities and engage with philanthropy and civil society", these reports have failed to clearly integrate and/or recognise the role of societal engagement, science communication and journalism, for effectively responding to societal challenges and delivering real-impact for citizens.

We believe the recommendations in this report can highlight some of the gaps and encourage the necessary structural changes, recognition and funding.

Fostering impactful research, practice and innovation in science

communication and collaboration

amongst its associated workforce within member states, can further **boost EU's competitive excellence and its top talent**, in a sustainable way, whilst creating a **trustworthy ecosystem for citizens' meaningful involvement**. We cannot neglect that these acquire special relevance in the current geopolitical context and polarisation, in the onset of constant polycrisis, such as those related to climate, health or AI, where attacks to academic freedom and scientific organisations can hinder trust and democracy^{9,10}, while an active public engagement in science can increase trust, foster critical thinking and contribute to the fight against misinformation.

⁶ Draghi, M. (2024). The future of European competitiveness – A competitiveness strategy for Europe. https://commission.europa.eu/topics/strengthening-european-competitiveness/eu-competitiveness-looking-ahead_en

⁷ Letta, E. (2024). Much more than a market – Speed, Security, Solidarity. Empowering the Single Market to deliver a sustainable future and prosperity for all EU Citizens. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/ny3j24sm/much-more-than-a-market-report-by-enrico-letta.pdf>

⁸ European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (2024). Align, act, accelerate – Research, technology and innovation to boost European competitiveness, Publications Office of the European Union, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/9106236>

⁹ DeLong, K, et al. (2024). Policy Brief on excellent science communication for urgent societal challenges. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11082053>

¹⁰ Moreno-Castro, C., et al. (2025). Strategies to address critical challenges to effective science–society relations, including misinformation and trust. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13309683>

2 Evidence and main findings

2.1 Motivations for effective science communication

- **Promotes democracy and an informed society:** scicomm helps improve democratic processes by ensuring the public is well-informed about scientific developments and supports evidence-informed policies.
- **Increases scientific literacy and awareness:** effective scicomm raises awareness and understanding of scientific concepts among the general public.
- **Brings personal and professional satisfaction:** researchers and communicators often find personal fulfilment and professional satisfaction in communicating science.
- **Attracts funding and collaborations:** engaging in scicomm can attract funding opportunities and foster scientific collaborations.
- **Expands career opportunities:** new job positions in scicomm offer researchers alternative career pathways, including roles as mediators for stakeholder engagement. Scicomm professionals can help enhance analytical thinking, empathy, and creative thinking in the public by making science accessible, relatable, and engaging—three of the 26 essential skills highlighted in the [Future of Jobs Report 2023](#), by the World Economic Forum. These developments align with ERA Policy Agenda - Action 17, which promotes recognition of the research management profession.
- **Engages citizens in science:** participatory, community-driven and citizen science initiatives enhance public engagement and participation in scientific research. These developments align with ERA Policy Agenda - Action 14, which brings science closer to citizens.
- **Promotes trust:** new media formats, inclusive representation of diverse researchers, and professionally mediated science communication and journalism can promote trustworthy and responsible communication, counter misinformation, and foster constructive dialogue. The Global Alliance for Public Relations and Communication Management, [addressed](#) the United Nations in July 2024, endorsing a global call to establish "Responsible Communication" as a Sustainable Development Goal - SDG18.

- **Improves scientific advancement:** science communication participatory approaches can push for a paradigm shift by enabling active listening and collaboration between researchers with multiple stakeholders, opening the knowledge generation process to new perspectives and research questions contextualised in current societal needs.
- **Leads to innovation:** several EU-funded projects foster the creation of new products and services in science communication and journalism that can bring more accessible and engaging scientific content and data visualisation, fostering greater public awareness and informed-decision making. For example, the [ENJOI Observatory](#) contains a series of prototypes that can lead to novel tools and applications.
- **Promotes diversity, intersectionality, and inclusion in science communication, while addressing historical biases:** initiatives that are based in the following guiding principles offer opportunities to reflect our societies: 1- respond to requests from diverse communities and cultures (responsiveness); 2- apply diversity as a guiding principle (sources, contents, distribution model); 3- plan an engagement strategy in the whole life-cycle of scientific-based information; 4- adopt the lens of intersectionality; 5- deal with the impact of colonialism on scientific ecosystem and 6- explore solutions/approaches enabling people to act.

2.2 Barriers for effective science communication

Three different levels were considered to define the main barriers that hinder the road to effective science communication and its impact: organisational, environmental and individual.

2.2.1 Organisational

- **Poor strategic, institutional support and structural funding:** science communication is frequently deprioritized by research institutions and funding bodies, resulting in inadequate support. Funding schemes seldom consider the time, budget, specialised expertise, and other resources essential for impactful, long-term initiatives. Additionally, complex governance structures and varying policies across Member States further complicate efforts to coordinate science communication. Often, communication of science (methods, process, academic system, research agenda, etc.) takes a back seat within institutions in favour of promoting individual research outcomes and growing their own visibility. To create a more meaningful impact, however, institutions should prioritise inter-institutional cooperation over competition, emphasising

collective scientific achievements over individual reputation-building. Finally, a lack of internal guidelines to protect scientific organisations and scientists may hinder public participation or media/social media exposure due to harassment and attacks resulting from misinformation and polarisation.

- Lack of training opportunities, skills and competences:** there is no formal training of scicomm in STEAM degrees nor lifelong training opportunities that prepare researchers in all career stages to engage and communicate to different target audiences. Many researchers lack formal training in scicomm, open science or research integrity, resulting in a lack of confidence and effectiveness in their communication efforts. Moreover, there is a generalised need for future-skills adaptation that allow upskilling of scicomm professionals in fast-growing digital society with AI-assisted tools, fact-checking, as well as community-driven and participatory methods and their social impact.

2.2.2 Environmental

- Limited accessibility:** opportunities are predominantly available to a minority, such as university staff or employees in large companies with dedicated departments.
- Exclusivity and limited audience reach:** scicomm efforts often fail to engage diverse audiences, remaining confined to specific groups interested in science or those with certain demographic characteristics like socioeconomic status, education level, etc. At the same time, the scientific community is perceived as an exclusive environment dominated by white Western perspectives, which can hinder wider public participation and diverse role models.
- Lack of user-friendly tools:** the lack of user-friendly tools and processes available to the public to access and make sense of the freely available data.

2.2.3 Individual

- Limited professional recognition, lack of defined career paths and stable job positions:** the absence of stable and professional scicomm job positions hampers the development of a dedicated scicomm workforce and its professionalisation, which may inherently affect women¹¹. Moreover, limited incentives

¹¹ Wilkinson, C., et al. (2022). Roles, incentives, training and audiences for science communication: perspectives from female science communicators JCOM 21(04), A04. <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.21040204>

and recognition for researchers hinder their full participation in scicomm activities. Both [DORA](#) and [CoARA](#) are still in early stages, and clear metrics for a “team science approach” are needed. Whilst the European Commission is advancing on the [European Competence Framework for Researchers](#) and the [European Competence Framework for Research Managers](#) is being conducted for the New European Research Area, under ERA Action 17, with defined skills and competences, we are still far from a clear and dedicated pathway for career progression in science communication.

- **Time constraints and bureaucratic burdens:** researchers face significant time constraints and administrative burdens, limiting their ability to engage in scicomm. Although not all researchers are meant to do scicomm, measures should be taken to guarantee access to a variety of science related careers beyond academic research, including careers with a focus on science communication.
- **Fear of misunderstanding and discredit:** concerns about being misunderstood by the public or discredited by peers, or unstable and polarised political climate of the country, discourage researchers from participating in scicomm, as participation in such activities may be seen as unprofessional or a deviation from rigorous academic standard, or lead to harassment, potentially limiting a broader dissemination and impact of scientific knowledge.

3 Policy recommendations

1. **Professionalise scicomm strengthening EU-wide institutional support:** encourage shift in organisational culture towards sustained support and funding for scicomm practices, research and innovation, facilitate exchange of knowledge, and mutual learning opportunities.
2. **Integrate scicomm, public engagement and societal impact in research portfolios:** integrate (evidence-informed) scicomm activities and impact assessment into the evaluation and funding criteria for research organisations, projects and individual researchers. Define key indicators and incentives for reward and recognition at multiple levels, integrating a gender perspective in monitoring and evaluation processes.
3. **Support career pathways in public R&I organisations and independent professionals in scicomm and journalism:** improve the working conditions of professional science communicators and journalists, as well as interdisciplinary profiles in research teams, to ensure innovative, high-quality and trustworthy communication. Support upskilling and new competences acquisition that respond to rapid societal challenges and the digital transformation.
4. **Establish infrastructures, training, guidelines and resources to boost future-proof skills:** establish capacity building infrastructures, develop and/or provide tailored training towards the needs of different professional profiles, accounting to sociodemographic characteristics, such as gender¹² and intersectionality. Promote guidelines for effective science-media interaction and other stakeholders, as well as specific protocols to deal with scicomm-based harassment, integrity and ethics. Facilitate access to high-quality scicomm resources, tools and content representing multiple cultural contexts and languages.
5. **Strengthen the open science policy and make open data the rule for every institution:** improve equitable access and transparent data-sharing practices to public engagement tools and scientific resources for diverse audiences, adopting an international-wide code for transparency to be used by all platforms and media.
6. **Facilitate collaboration between researchers and policymakers:** provide science communication tools, guidelines and dedicated programmes that can be effective in approaching the science-policy ecosystems, fostering science advocacy and evidence-informed policies.

¹² Revuelta, G. et al. (2023). La comunicación científica en España. FECYT <https://doi.org/10.58121/gvn9-h856>;

7. **Facilitate researchers–citizens dialogue:** promote participatory initiatives that foster dialogue between researchers and citizens, enhancing mutual understanding and trust. Support bottom-up, community- or citizen-driven scicomm initiatives for mutual benefits that respond more directly to societal needs and facilitate access to knowledge.
8. **Support collaboration between researchers and journalists and across sectors:** promote collaboration between researchers, communicators, policymakers, the media and the private sector to increase mutual trust and enhance the impact and reach of science through quality-based scicomm, public engagement and journalism.
9. **Support fact-checking and reliable scientific information:** encourage and support fact-checking and tackling misinformation initiatives and the dissemination of accurate and trustworthy information and reliable sources.
10. **Encourage scicomm and journalism knowledge valorisation towards society and the market:** encourage innovation, the establishment of new companies and sustainable business models that may result from projects (including developments in digital media platforms, AI-based tools, art-science activities, etc), opening new markets and job opportunities.

4 Final Remarks

Multiple stakeholders, including funders and policymakers at different governance levels, play a **pivotal role in strengthening science communication across Europe** by implementing the strategies outlined in this policy brief. To foster trust, scientific literacy, and democratic engagement, it is essential to prioritize science communication within institutional and funding frameworks. This entails **integrating science communication** into research evaluation criteria, supporting professional career pathways, and ensuring equitable access to training and resources.

Investing in participatory, inclusive, and evidence-informed science communication initiatives, can **bridge the gap between science and society**, enabling citizens to make informed decisions and actively participate in shaping research agendas. Additionally, fostering cross-sector collaborations and supporting fact-checking initiatives will counter misinformation and ensure that **science communication upholds transparency and credibility**.

Ultimately, by addressing structural, environmental, and individual barriers, funders, policy and decision makers can support **creating an ecosystem where science communication thrives, contributing to societal resilience, innovation, and trust in science**. In a crucial moment where defining the FP10 programme and budget is an important milestone for the future of R&I in Europe, commitment to these actions need to be ensured to empower communities, advance scientific progress, and promote evidence-informed policymaking.

5 Methodology

During the period of 2019–2023, the 8 SwafS-19 sister projects conducted several participatory exercises (co-creation sessions, citizens consultation, etc.), reaching more than 3.000 people across the EU (Austria, Hungary, Estonia, Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, The Netherlands), the United Kingdom and beyond. An overview is provided in Table 1. These included as stakeholders: citizens, researchers, policymakers, industry

representatives, journalists and science communication professionals which led to the understanding of the state of the art in science communication and a general landscape of its recognition, funding and professionalisation. The analysis of all policy briefs and recommendations produced by these projects constitutes the basis for this document.

Table 1. Research Methodology overview.

	Type of research	SwafS-19 project	Number of participants	Countries
Quadruple helix stakeholders engagement (NEWSERA Labs)	Qualitative in-person focus groups	NEWSERA	240	ES, PT, IT, BE
Citizen engagement	Citizen consultation	CONCISE	1297 (representative sample)	ES, PT, IT, SK, PL
Stakeholder engagement	Qualitative in-person focus groups	ENJOI	180	ES, PT, IT, BE
Stakeholder engagement	Survey, longitudinal diary study and stakeholder consultation sessions	GlobalSCAPE	1046	EU+
Stakeholder engagement (ReThinker Labs)	Qualitative in-person focus groups	ReThink	100	UK, NL, SE, PO, SE, IT, PT
Stakeholder engagement	Qualitative interviews and desk research	TRESCA	60	AU, NL, ES, HU
Stakeholder engagement	Qualitative online focus groups and online surveys	QUEST	160	EU+
Citizen engagement	Citizen consultation	PARCOS	500	FI, UK, BE

6 References

NEWSERA

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TRESCA

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QUEST

Matteo Di Rosa, Claudia Iasillo, Ilda Mannino, Alessandra Fornetti, Enrico Costa, Roberta Villa, & Fabiana Zollo. (2021) [D4.4: Recommendations on Policies and Incentives for Quality Science Communication](#). QUEST project. EU Horizon 2020, GA No 824634.

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GlobalSCAPE

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ParCOS

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PARCOS Knutas A., Wolff, A., Hudson L. (2022) [Final policy brief deliverable 7.8](#). Lappeenranta, Finland. ParCos project. EU Horizon 2020, GA No 872500.

ENJOI

ENJOI project (2023) [Short policy brief RP2: How to support a healthy communication environment? Effectively combating global challenges with good science communication and journalism](#). ENJOI project. EU Horizon 2020, GA No 101006407.

RETHINK

Roedema T, Rerimassie V & Kupper F (2020) [Incentive and Disincentive Structures for R&I Stakeholders to Engage in SciComm](#). Deliverable 2.1. RETHINK project. EU Horizon 2020, GA No 824573.

CONCISE

Llorente, C and Revuelta, G (2020) [Hurdles and incentives to science communication in Europe](#). CONCISE project. EU Horizon 2020, GA No 824537.

7 Project details

PROJECT NAME Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe (COALESCE)

PARTNERS

COALESCE PROJECT WEBSITE

<https://coalesceproject.eu>

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